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Full Length Article

Marine plastic entrepreneurship; Exploring drivers, barriers and value creation in the blue economy

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History:

Received 6 April 2022

Accepted 10 May 2022

Available online xxx

Key words:

Marine plastic

Sustainable business models

Sustainable entrepreneurship

ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurs working to tackle marine challenges are contributing to the Blue Economy by developing new technologies, services and products that can simultaneously stimulate economic growth and deliver environmental benefits. We study a subset of these blue entrepreneurs focused on marine plastic pollution mitigation, since little is known about the business models deployed and their associated drivers and barriers in this emerging industry. We utilize a multiple case study approach to analyze the business models of 96 startups working to manage marine plastic and identify four business model categories: 1) consumer targeted solutions, 2) government and business solutions, 3) companies focused on value chain development, and 4) startups that generate revenue to fund plastic waste recovery. These four BMs differ in how they create environmental benefits, as well as their economic value capture or revenue models. We then conducted 19 interviews with entrepreneurs (20% of the sample) and six experts to understand the conditions that support or hinder business model development. We find that entrepreneurial challenges and motivations associated with starting a new business are experienced by all companies, regardless of the business model chosen. Other relevant drivers include the availability of financing early on in business development, a supportive culture and positive and constructive market response. Challenges include competition from less sustainable businesses that may negatively influence the legitimacy of the industry, as well as slow government responses. Finally, we propose recommendations for policy makers to encourage blue entrepreneurship and for practitioners to prepare for identified barriers and predict avenues of support.

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1. Introduction

The term Blue Economy emerged in 2012 at the United Nations Convention on Sustainable Development and is now widely applied in marine policy and governance (Wenhai et al., 2019). Though competing definitions exist, most refer to the dual importance of the ocean: first, as a critical ecosystem deserving conservation and protection, and second as a source of livelihoods and opportunity that should be capitalized upon (Voyer, Quirk, McIlgorm & Azmi, 2018). One pathway to stimulate the Blue Economy is through development of new technologies, like ocean renewable energy systems, or commercializing new products, for example algae bioplastics (Soma, van den Burg, Hoefnagel, Stuiver & van der Heide, 2018; Wenhai et al., 2019). These products or technologies can be supported by governments or spearheaded by research institutes, but may also be introduced by the private sector. Entrepreneurship for

the Blue Economy, hereafter called blue entrepreneurship, has grown in recent years, evidenced by an increase in accelerators, innovation prizes and investment firms supporting ocean technologies and startups (Dijkstra, van Beukering & Brouwer, 2021; Katapult Ocean, 2020). We use the term blue entrepreneurship to differentiate from green entrepreneurship, also called ecopreneurship or environmental entrepreneurship. Green entrepreneurship is the process of 'exploiting economic opportunities that are present in environmentally relevant market failures' (Dean & McMullen, 2007 p. 58) by 'catering to environmental challenges and creating economic value' (Haldar, 2019, p. 1165). As such, we define blue entrepreneurship as the process of creating a new, economically viable business model by catering to marine environmental challenges, and thus supporting the Blue Economy (Dean & McMullen, 2007; Haldar, 2019).

One marine environmental challenge that has been steadily gaining attention is plastic pollution. Plastic is currently overwhelming global waste management infrastructures, yet production continues to rise, and a portion of this waste eventually ends up in marine environments (Borrelle et al., 2020). This pollution threatens the

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environment and economy by harming marine life, damaging fishing gear and spoiling tourist destinations (Beaumont et al., 2019; Jambeck et al., 2020). These issues have been exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic which has seen a rise in plastic personal protective equipment (PPE) and disposable food packaging, coupled with government rollbacks of policies such as single-use plastics bans (Canning-Clode, Sepúlveda, Almeida & Monteiro, 2020; Okuku et al., 2020; Patrício Silva et al., 2020). As production rises, marine plastic pollution prevention and management will continue to be a global priority requiring innovative solutions.

Startups and entrepreneurs are uniquely positioned to provide such innovative solutions. They can be more radical than incumbent firms and quickly act to fill unexploited niches, for example by developing new environmental management products and services (Hockerts & Wüstenhagen, 2009; Lüdeke-Freund, 2020; Schaltegger, Lüdeke-Freund & Hansen, 2016). If sustainable startups can establish themselves, proliferate and increase their scale of operation, they have the potential to mitigate the challenge of ocean plastic pollution. However, no studies have investigated the enabling conditions that support or hinder the development of new marine plastic focused ventures, and this study seeks to fill this research gap.

The paper answers the following two research questions. First, what specific types of business models are deployed by blue entrepreneurs working on marine plastics, and second, what drivers and barriers are experienced by these entrepreneurs? We know from previous research that a wide variety of business models exist, and the design of the business model contributes to the success of a new sustainable venture (Long, Looijen & Blok, 2018; Trimi, Berbegal-Mirabent, Trimi & Berbegal-Mirabent, 2012). A business model is the economic logic that defines how a firm creates and captures value for themselves, shareholders and other stakeholders (Tece, 2010). The design of the business model is influenced by the firm's context and will lead to different sets of challenges and opportunities (Vermunt, Negro, Verweij, Kuppens & Hekkert, 2019). Therefore, we hypothesize that key drivers and barriers will differ for entrepreneurs deploying different types of business models within our sample of marine plastic companies. To test this, we develop categories of business models that cluster similar companies together. This allows for analysis within similar groups of cases, and for cross-sectional analysis between differing groups. The latter constitutes the novelty of the research presented in this paper.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the current literature in terms of sustainable business models and entrepreneurial drivers and barriers. In Section 3 we explain the methodology including data collection and analysis. Section 4 systematically presents the results and discusses the main findings. Section 5 concludes the paper and provides recommendations for future research.

2. Literature review

2.1. Sustainable business models

A business model (BM) is a framework that demonstrates how a firm creates and captures value. The model is a tool to understand, monitor or change a firm's strategy and BMs are used in industry and academia in many different applications (Tece, 2010; Zott, Amit & Massa, 2011). For example, frameworks such as the Business Model Canvas are used to help entrepreneurs define and communicate their business ideas, or for established firms to experiment with potential changes to business practices (Boons, Montalvo, Quist & Wagner, 2013; Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010; Osterwalder, Pigneur & Tucci, 2005). Accordingly, a sustainable business model (SBM) is an extension of the BM concept designed to account for sustainable development goals (Jolink & Niesten, 2015). SBMs include environmental and social sources of costs and benefits and recognize that value can be provided for a variety of stakeholders beyond the focal firm and its

shareholders (Freudenreich, Lüdeke-Freund & Schaltegger, 2019). In doing so, SBMs often deviate from traditional profit maximization value logics to include goals such as job creation and environmental protection (Morioka, Bolis, Evans & Carvalho, 2017).

In academia, SBM frameworks are used to distill the complex workings of a business into its key elements (Bocken, Short, Rana & Evans, 2014; Nosratabadi et al., 2019). This allows researchers to define, compare, and analyze a firm or group of firms. SBMs can be categorized based on similarities in, for example, revenue models, customer relationships or environmental benefits (Tukker, 2004; Zufall, Norris, Schaltegger, Revellio & Hansen, 2020). These categories, or patterns, can be used as inspiration for industry or as a classification tool for research (Lüdeke-Freund, Bohnsack, Breuer & Massa, 2019). For example, an influential study identified 45 sustainable business innovation patterns in 11 groups through literature review and expert consultation (Lüdeke-Freund, Carroux, Joyce, Massa & Breuer, 2018a). These patterns were then judged based on sustainable value creation: primarily economic, social or ecological or a combination thereof. Patterns and typologies have also been developed for subgroups of businesses, such as circular BMs (Henry, Bauwens, Hekkert & Kirchherr, 2020; Lüdeke-Freund, Gold & Bocken, 2018b), or very specific industries, such as forest-based bio-economy BMs (D'Amato, Veijonaho & Toppinen, 2020) or sustainable smart phone BMs (Zufall et al., 2020).

In order to develop categorizations, businesses must be described and defined by a set of BM elements. These range from the nine elements in the Business Model Canvas to a three element approach including value proposition, value creation and delivery, and value capture (Bocken et al., 2014; Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). Regardless of the number of elements, each framework includes a variable to describe the main good or service being offered, the relationships with customers and supply chain partners, and the means of capturing revenues (Méndez-León, Reyes-Carrillo & Díaz-Pichardo, 2021).

Thus, a challenge in SBM research is choosing which framework to apply, as study outcomes will depend on the variables used to describe the business. Critics note that frameworks are 'useful to describe *what* SBMs may look like, but provide little perspective to understand *how* the business models actually work to create lasting value for stakeholders' (Dembek, York & Singh, 2018, p. 1603). To address this, Dembek et al. (2018) applied an activities perspective in their study of 55 Base of the Pyramid business models. The activities perspective defines a business by its ongoing processes and dynamic relationships (Méndez-León et al., 2021; Zott & Amit, 2010). In this research, we choose the BM elements of value proposition, economic value creation and capture, and ecological value creation and capture, while further describing how stakeholders are involved in these BM activities (Dembek et al., 2018; Rosca, Arnold & Bendul, 2017; Zott & Amit, 2010; Zufall et al., 2020). By describing each business using these variables, we can then cluster companies together based on similar activities and stakeholder relationships.

2.2. Drivers and barriers to sustainable entrepreneurship

Sustainable entrepreneurship is the study of new ventures and entrepreneurs who are trying to achieve environmental and/or social goals through business (Burch et al., 2016; Haldar, 2019; Muñoz & Cohen, 2018; Schlange, 2014). To reach their goals, these start-ups must deliver a successful BM by exploiting an entrepreneurial opportunity (Gümüşay, 2018; Kuckertz, Hinderer & Röhm, 2019). Considering sustainability, entrepreneurial opportunities can look like (1) catering to growing numbers of green or eco-conscious consumers, (2) developing products from alternative or underutilized sources such as algae or waste, (3) platforms to rent goods or services, or (4) managing environmental threats such as climate change or ocean pollution (Cohen & Winn, 2007; Kuckertz et al., 2019).

Table 1

Literature review on drivers and barriers to sustainable entrepreneurship taken from (Caldera et al., 2019; Cantele et al., 2020; De Jesus & Mendonça, 2017; Gast et al., 2017; Hörisch, 2015; Long et al., 2018; Lüdeke-Freund, 2020; Santarelli & Vivarelli, 2007; Woolthuis, 2010; Yadav et al., 2018).

Categories	Drivers	Barriers
Internal factors	Entrepreneurial	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Entrepreneur and employee ambition - Leadership - Sustainability orientation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited time, knowledge and business acumen - Lack of leadership
External factors	Technical	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability of (enabling) technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of technical support or technical capital
	Economic and market	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumer or supply chain demands - Favorable markets - Cost reduction - Expected competitive advantage - Access to financial capital 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competition with incumbents - Lack of financing - Uncertain returns and risks - Short-term vs long-term investment requirements
	Institutional and regulatory	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accelerator or incubator programs - Pro-environmental legislation or regulation - Economic or structural support - Knowledge sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deficient or harmful regulations or legislation - Lack of support
	Socio-cultural	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shifting consumer preferences and public awareness - Stakeholder involvement - Influence of community and environmental groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rigidity of consumer behaviors and business structures

As entrepreneurs work to exploit opportunities and develop BMs, they must grapple with the contextual conditions that can support or hinder their ability to achieve financial viability and produce environmental benefits. There is a growing body of research into drivers and barriers for sustainable entrepreneurs in general, or into specific sub-groups such as the sustainable food and beverage industry (Jolink & Niesten, 2015; Long et al., 2018). Some studies define the context as an ecosystem comprised of the physical, social and regulatory structures and networks available to support developing ventures (Bischoff, 2019; Henry et al., 2020; Neumeier & Santos, 2018). Others describe the external influencing conditions as 'hard' (i.e. technical and economic) or 'soft' (i.e. regulatory and socio-cultural) factors that have the potential to be both an obstacle or enabler (De Jesus & Mendonça, 2017). In addition, internal factors related to the capabilities and personal motivations of the individual entrepreneur are frequently researched and considered to be a critical determinant of venture success (Gast, Gundolf & Cesinger, 2017; Patzelt & Shepherd, 2011).

In Table 1, we present a summary of five categories of drivers and barriers found in the sustainable entrepreneurship literature. These five factors will be explicitly studied in our research to assess the extent they have influenced entrepreneurs working on marine plastic and the Blue Economy.

Another facet of entrepreneurship research focuses on the process of developing a new venture (i.e. the entrepreneurial journey), from the ideation stage towards acquiring resources, managing growth, and reaching maturity, or otherwise declining or failing (Choi & Gray, 2008; Santarelli & Vivarelli, 2007). Some studies focus on the entire entrepreneurship journey, and search for causal relationships and patterns of development (Kibler, Fink, Lang & Muñoz, 2015; Muñoz, Cacciotti & Cohen, 2018). Others try to analyze what elements, such as motivation or strategy, may contribute to venture development and success (Choi & Gray, 2008; Dickel, 2018). Our study conceptualizes entrepreneurship as an ongoing process with many influencing factors, and seeks to find patterns or trends among similar groups of sustainable entrepreneurs (Long et al., 2018).

2.3. Analytical framework

To develop our analytical approach, this paper adopts concepts and theories from two research streams: SBM and sustainable entrepreneurship. The unit of analysis is thus a new venture operating an SBM to manage marine plastic. As a baseline for the current paper, we use a database of 105 startups working on marine plastic management (Dijkstra et al., 2021). This sample of companies is both young and small, consisting of companies in the early stages of their

entrepreneurial journey, who are still in the process of developing and deploying their business models, managing challenges and seeking support. Marine plastic pollution only became a global challenge with significant investment and political attention in the past 5–10 years, and therefore we consider the sample to be representative of the nascent industry of marine plastic solutions (Dijkstra et al., 2021; Karasik et al., 2020; Moss, Eldson & Jambeck, 2017).

A sustainable venture can be considered successful if the company is capturing and delivering environmental and economic value, but we recognize that this can be done in a myriad of ways, in other words, through a variety of SBMs (Neumeier & Santos, 2018). The journey towards a successful BM is influenced by both the internal company conditions, such as the flexibility, capabilities and resources of the entrepreneur, as well as external factors including technology availability, the regulatory environment, market conditions and societal acceptance (De Jesus & Mendonça, 2017; Long et al., 2018). The study will empirically assess if these internal and external factors are relevant for certain groups of marine plastic ventures. The variables constituting our analytical framework are defined in detail in Appendix 1.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research design

We utilize a multiple case study approach for our study of marine plastic entrepreneurs and collect data from publicly available sources as well as interviews with company representatives (Yin, 2003). The methodology is modeled on previous studies that have analyzed BMs for a large number of companies with the goal of developing typologies and identifying similarities and differences (Dembek et al., 2018; Henry et al., 2020; Rosca et al., 2017). The case study approach is commonly used in SBM research as it can result in a structured yet in-depth description of a complex real-world phenomenon, i.e. a business. Since our research involves a large amount of companies, this is facilitated through a pre-defined analytical framework of elements, see Appendix 1 (Hahn, Spieth & Ince, 2018). The case companies and marine plastic industry are relatively young; therefore, our approach is exploratory and we do not attempt to test a hypothesis or prove a theory. Further supporting the exploratory nature is the inclusion of semi-structured interviews with entrepreneurs and experts to provide insights into the enabling environment and challenges faced in BM development, similar to methods applied by D'Amato et al. (2020), Long et al. (2018), and Vermunt et al. (2019).

To answer the first research question (what specific types of business models are deployed by blue entrepreneurs working on marine

Table 2

Description of anonymized interviewees. Size refers to number of employees listed on LinkedIn. Micro = under 10, Small = 11–50.

BM group	Startup	Description	Year	Size	
Consumer solutions	1	ConsumerDevice	Consumer device for capturing microfibers	2018	Micro
	2	MicrofiberTech	Various solutions for capturing microfibers	2017	Micro
Government and industry solutions	3	RiverBarrier1	River barrier for capturing plastics	2018	Micro
	4	RiverBarrier2	River barrier for capturing plastics	2019	Micro
	5	BoatCollection1	Boat designed to collect plastics	2018	Micro
	6	BoatCollection2	Boats and drones designed to collect plastics	2013	Micro
	7	EnergySystem1	Small scale system for pyrolyzing plastic	2010	Small
	8	EnergySystem2	Micro scale system for pyrolyzing plastic	2012	Micro
	9	LitterMapping1	Software application and services for mapping plastic	2011	Small
Value chain development	10	LitterMapping2	Software application and services for mapping plastic	2012	Micro
	11	Awareness	Consulting and services for plastic education	2011	Micro
	12	FishingNets	Fishing net aggregation	2017	Micro
	13	NetsRecycler	Fishing net collection and transformation	2019	Micro
	14	RecycledProducts	Manufacturing recycled products	2013	Micro
	15	MarketDeveloper1	Whole value chain development for fishing nets	2013	Micro
	16	MarketDeveloper2	Whole value chain development for a number of plastic polymers	2018	Small
Funding plastic waste recovery	17	FinancingWaste1	Selling offsets to fund waste management	2016	Micro
	18	FinancingWaste2	Selling offsets to fund waste management	2019	Small
	19	FinancingWaste3	Selling offsets and/or tokens to fund waste management	2019	Micro

plastics?), we use a multiple case study database and produce a BM classification framework. The second research question (what drivers and barriers experienced by these entrepreneurs?) will be answered using results from semi-structured interviews. Synthesizing the results, we can determine if key drivers and barriers are commonly experienced or more relevant for certain categories of marine plastic business models.

3.2. Data collection

The first source of data is a database of startups and small and medium enterprises (SMEs) working on marine plastic. The methodology and descriptive analysis of the database can be found in [Dijkstra et al. \(2021\)](#). The database has been modified and updated to (1) add companies that were missed or founded after the original article was submitted in 2020, and (2) further describe the BMs based on the new analytical framework. For many companies, this could be done using data gathered during the previous study, but it involved revisiting documents and notes in order to confirm the additional BM characteristics. Further information was sourced from websites, social media pages and company reports, as well as external sources such as news articles, blogs or other documents that feature the company. Recent papers analyzing marine plastic management technologies were also used to identify further cases or details ([Bellou et al., 2021](#); [Helinski, Wolfand & Poor, 2021](#); [Schmaltz et al., 2020](#)) Using publicly available data to describe the key features of businesses is a well-established methodology applied in SBM research ([Ciulli & Kolk, 2019](#); [Hahn et al., 2018](#); [Henry et al., 2020](#)). The complete database of companies described by their SBM elements can be found in the Supplementary Materials and contains 96 cases.

The second source of data are semi-structured interviews conducted with 19 entrepreneurs and six experts in the marine plastic solutions industry. We use stratified purposeful sampling in order to select interviewees from the database belonging to the different BM categories to ensure responses from each group. The 19 entrepreneur interviews represent approximately 20% of the companies in the database and anonymized descriptions are shown in [Table 2](#). It should be noted that the sample may be biased based on entrepreneurs who were willing to participate in the interview. We also sought interviews with companies attending conferences and workshop with the researchers and those connected to the researcher's networks.

The interview guide asked questions about BM activities and relationships and covered the five categories of influencing factors: entrepreneurial, economic, technical, regulatory and socio-cultural.

Entrepreneur respondents were asked about their experiences with each factor, how it has been a driver or barrier for their business specifically and how significant the factor was.

Experts were asked to comment more generally on each factor and how the context can be both an enabler or obstacle, descriptions of the experts are included in [Table 3](#). All interviews were transcribed for full accuracy and the semi-structured interview guide is included in [Appendix 2](#).

3.3. Data analysis and coding

The business models of the 96 companies in the database were coded and explored to see if trends or patterns of business cases emerged. The goal was to identify groups of similar business cases, reduce complexity and allow for comparisons between groups instead of between individual cases. As can be seen in the database included in the Supplementary Materials, we simplified the complex sustainable business model of each case company into seven variables. Following previous work on SBM patterns, we explored the sample by arranging the cases into groups based on similarities to search for a logical organization ([Dembek et al., 2018](#); [Rosca et al., 2017](#); [Zufall et al., 2020](#)). For example, we clustered all cases with a similar revenue model together and further by the customers targeted. Exploring the data was facilitated through the use of tables and matrixes and included multiple iterations. Eventually, we identified a coherent structure by grouping companies with similar environmental value creation and economic value capture mechanisms. This resulted in four main business model categories, described in detail in [Section 4.1](#). The identified business categories were presented at the New Business Models Conference in 2021 in order to get feedback and improve upon the classifications.

The data gathered in the interviews includes verbatim transcripts as well as notes taken by the researchers. To analyze the interview data, an inductive and deductive analysis of transcripts and notes was done using the qualitative data analysis software ATLAS.ti 8 ([Henry et al., 2020](#); [Long et al., 2018](#)). The text was uploaded into ATLAS.ti 8 and coded using pre-defined codes (deductive) and open codes (inductive) in an iterative process. The pre-defined codes aligned with the variables in the analytical framework, such as the external and internal factors, environmental and economic value creation and delivery and stakeholder relationships (see [Appendix 1](#)). At the same time, open coding was used to explore tensions, opportunities, relationships and experiences based on the individual entrepreneur's experience and allowed for insights that went beyond the

Table 3
Description of expert interviewees.

	Expert interviews	Description
1	Expert1	Entrepreneur and consultant focused on plastic
2	Expert2	Founder of sustainable solutions platform with a focus on plastics
3	Expert3	Founder of a company developing plastic alternatives
4	Expert4	Founder of NGO specializing in plastic waste management
5	Expert5	SME representative focused on marine pollution cleanup
6	Expert6	Business developer involved in marine plastic waste recycling

Table 4
Four business model categories based on environmental and economic value creation and capture.

Business model	Environmental value creation	Economic value capture
1. Solutions for consumers	Value created by consumers	Value captured for company
2. Solutions for industry and governments	Environmental value created by users, industry and governments	Value captured for company
3. Value chain development	Value created by actors in the value chain	Value captured for companies in the value chain
4. Funding plastic waste recovery	Value created by third-party organizations	Value captured for focal company and third-party organizations

analytical framework, including additional codes related to upscaling and impact measurement.

The initial coding was done comprehensively but without a search for patterns and meaning. For example, one paragraph on technological development could contain a dozen overlapping codes if the text referred to a driver, barrier, tension, partnership and value capture mechanism. After the first round, the codebook was scrutinized to determine if there were codes that should be combined or divided. For example, rather than having codes for 'financial partnerships', 'investors' and 'venture capital', these were combined into 'financing and capital'. The interviews were then revisited with the updated codebook. Finally, to understand similarities and differences between business models, the coded text was analyzed per business model category and the outcomes are presented in the results section.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Business model categories

The BM categories identified were 1) solutions that were sold to and used by consumers to prevent marine plastic pollution, 2) services and products for marine plastic management marketed towards governments, municipalities or industry, 3) companies involved in developing the global value chain for marine plastics, and 4) businesses who gained profits in order to fund plastic cleanup efforts. As shown in Table 4, these four BM categories were delineated based on their different environmental value creation and economic value capture mechanisms.

Although all the businesses create environmental value through the reduction of marine plastic pollution, this can be further segmented into four management strategies. These are (1) **prevention** of ocean pollution by stopping emissions from key leakage points like rivers and wastewater, (2) **collection** of marine plastic from the marine and coastal environments, (3) **transformation** of collected marine plastics through energy recovery or recycling, and (4) **monitoring** of marine plastics and knowledge generation (Dijkstra et al., 2021). In Dijkstra et al. (2021), prevention also includes the production of marine degradable plastic and plastic alternatives, such as algae bioplastics, which are not included in the present study. We made the choice to focus on traditional polymers and plastic materials for a more streamlined perspective of the value chain.

In Fig. 1, we plot the four BM categories against these four management strategies, showing the current strategies deployed as well as the unoccupied white spaces in the entrepreneurial landscape of marine plastic management. In the following sections, we will

describe each of the four BM categories focusing on typical characteristics of the business case, plastic management strategies and discussing frequently mentioned drivers and barriers identified in the interviews.

4.2. Consumer solutions

The startups operating this BM are focused on traditional consumer product sales for the prevention of marine plastic pollution. Thus, the value proposition targets environmentally conscious consumers by offering products they can use to minimize their own marine waste footprint. In our sample, the firms that operate the purely consumer sales model are technologies and systems that can be installed to prevent microplastic pollution from household washing machines. Accordingly, the environmental value delivery is also done by consumers who install a filter on their home washing machine. With only 6% of the sample, there are only few businesses represented, and they gain profit through product sales, using e-commerce or through brick and mortar distributors. To measure impact, these companies rely on sales figures, e.g. number of filters sold, with the assumption that these sales are translating to use of product and reduction of environmental impact from microplastics. This means that the environmental benefits are scaled when more consumers are reached, as put by one entrepreneur 'if we really want to create an impact, we need a lot of users' (MicrofiberTech).

In both interviews conducted, the respondents mentioned the importance of developing a minimum viable product to 'get something out there sooner rather than later. . .[and] inspire other innovations quickly' (ConsumerDevice). At the same time, there was a focus on ease of use, since the technologies would be used by consumers and needed to be simple to install and clean. Technical and scientific partnerships were important to pilot, produce and monitor the effectiveness of the developed systems. Crowdfunding was mentioned as a market driver which gave the companies access to a groundswell of early adopters. Looking to the future, one respondent noted that government regulation is necessary to integrate into mass markets, for example by requiring filters for new washing machines.

However, the push for regulation also leads to backlash, as one entrepreneur pointed out that 'there is lobbying going on, particularly from the washing machine producers' (MicrofiberTech). Incumbents in the fashion and appliance industry are reportedly interested but wary of new innovations for microplastic filtration. Different industries are involved in microfiber pollution, and many are trying to avoid responsibility for the problem while searching for ways to 'clear their bad conscious' (MicrofiberTech). The two interviewees

Fig. 1. Mapping the ventures based on MPM function and business model. Sample sizes per BM category and per function are given in brackets. Mapping inspired by Kuckertz et al. (2019).

mentioned blame shifting, weak regulations and prohibitive costs as obstacles to mass market adoption.

There is potential for future regulations to make filters obligatory on all washing machines, which give the entrepreneurs reason for optimism. Ongoing sales and customer use serve as a real-world demonstration that the products are effective. This data is ammunition against lobbying or political arguments that the devices are impractical or unfeasible. Furthermore, the startups are not only focused on sales and profit, but also on the power of an inspirational product. They want to give consumers a tangible means to reduce their marine waste footprint and encourage environmentally friendly behavior. These companies include awareness raising and improving scientific knowledge in their business practices through collaborations with education campaigns and researchers. This engagement with science also leads to accountability in the emerging industry, which is further supported by strong relationships with NGOs. Working with NGOs means the startups are held to high sustainability standards, which is reflected in their product design choices and end-of-life management strategies.

4.3. Industry and government solutions

A large number of solutions in the sample (52%) develop innovative technologies, processes or other solutions for marine plastic that are then utilized by industry and governments. Jointly, these companies target prevention, collection, transformation and monitoring, but they all specialize in a single type of marine litter management. Examples include the development of wastewater treatment systems, drones or boats to collect floating litter, pyrolysis machines and software solutions to monitor and map litter. To deliver environmental value, companies sell or license their technologies, systems or services to municipalities or environmental management organizations. For example, a river collection device may be sold to a municipality who uses it to capture and remove litter as part of their waste management services. In other cases, the focal firm maintains

ownership of the devices or systems and are contracted for services. Regardless of the implementation model, to increase the environmental benefits of businesses in this category, more government oversight and accountability for marine plastic is seen as necessary.

Many of the interviewees cited growing public outcry against marine plastic pollution as the main motivation to develop and market their solutions. They realized that governments were not adequately addressing the problem and moved to fill the niche. This ability to notice a gap in the market (i.e. the lack of effective marine plastic management) and innovate to quickly reach the market is a classic example of exploiting an entrepreneurial opportunity. A few startups even mentioned that they are having trouble keeping up with the pace of orders due to large customer interest. For some entrepreneurs, government support in the form of feasibility studies, pilot projects or research consortia was crucial in the early stages of development. This support benefits new companies financially, but also allows for collaborative development and feedback with potential future customers.

Most of the companies in this sample are involved in technology development. Not surprisingly, they highlight the availability of enabling technologies as a contributor to business success. For example, one company modified an existing boat to collect floating litter thereby ‘taking advantage of solutions that have been applied in the past to use for another purpose’ (RiverBarrier1). This helped them reach the market faster since these systems were already deployed in other functions. Conversely, other companies were commercializing a completely new device or process, in essence starting from scratch. This led to more challenges, as one respondent explained ‘even just collecting [plastic] with very simple technology is even more complicated than I thought’ (RiverBarrier2).

Throughout the interviews, the most important barrier mentioned was competition for funding and customers. Since marine plastic pollution has become a viral sensation, this has led to an explosion of grants and projects, but one entrepreneur noted that ‘it’s a huge mess... I don’t understand how it is working and this is frustrating. I

see a lot of money ending up in projects that are really not efficient. . . I think this could work better if there would be more transparency or honest communication' (RiverBarrier2). Startups struggle with the time-consuming process of writing grant or funding proposals, some of which have unclear guidelines, while also feeling the pressure since 'everyone is trying to compete for funding' (Litter-Mapping2). There are multiple benefits for startups to work on government projects and grants, such as feedback from potential users, relationships building and undiluted investment, but this has also led to steep competition.

Governments may also be complicated customers due to bureaucratic rules and regulations, such as generally strict conditions for public procurement. Furthermore, political support can shift as a result of new political leadership or exogenous shocks like an economic recession. One startup was contracted by a municipality to provide marine plastic collection services, but an economic downturn in 2010 led the municipality to cancel their contracts, which still have yet to be reinstated. In many countries, there is no legislation determining who is responsible for coastal or marine litter management, in which case no customer can be identified to market services to. As one respondent says, municipalities, ports and tourism authorities can all argue that 'we didn't produce it, so why do we have to manage it?' (EnergySystem2). An expert noted that for many industries 'marine pollution is a tragedy of the commons, the high seas are a no man's land. . . out of sight, out of mind. . . I don't need to deal with it' (Expert1). This lack of responsibility and blame shifting is a significant barrier to identifying customers and developing a profitable revenue model.

Another challenge is the lack of data and standardized metrics for plastic collection, recycling and management. Monitoring is not a standard practice, so governments and companies may not know the extent of their plastic problem, and therefore be unable or unwilling to effectively manage their waste. This also links to financing: without an established monitoring method for environmental benefits, investors do not have clear metrics to measure which companies or technologies are most effective. The companies themselves are grappling with 'how do you measure impact?' (BoatCollection1).

Many of the interviewees also commented on the importance of data and monitoring policies, not only as metrics to use when applying for financing, but also to improve the effectiveness of their own services. "The more you understand the movement of litter, the more cost efficient you can make the cleanups" (BoatCollection1) and this motivation leads the companies to invest in their own monitoring software or processes. This data may then be shared with the government or made public to advance scientific and general knowledge. Data and accountability generate a positive feedback loop for these companies since better information on where marine litter is and how much can be managed can lead to targeted legislation and policies to stimulate management, further increasing demand for marine plastic management services.

4.4. Value chain development

This BM category consists of companies working within the global value chain for recycled marine plastic, and includes highly networked businesses who rely on partners to deliver environmental benefits and secure economic profits. For these companies, which comprise of 29% of the sample, the driving economic logic is that the entire value chain needs to succeed in order for each actor in the chain to succeed. This requires a sufficient, stable and quality supply of material paired with a proportionate amount of market demand. Some companies in the sample participate in multiple stages of the value chain, for example collection and transformation, whereas others focus on a single stage. Startups in this category invest in relationships vertically and horizontally in the value chain: which is necessary due to the large amount of activities needed to recycle marine

plastics, such as collection, aggregation, processing, recycling and manufacturing. To stimulate demand and support the growth of the value chain, the companies in this category are focused on storytelling and marketing their products, processes and materials, for example through labeling and a strong social media presence.

These companies have recognized that the growing public awareness of plastic pollution could translate to customer demand for marine plastic products. The societal urgency around marine plastic is therefore a driver for entrepreneurs who want to solve the problem, and has led to consumers who are willing to pay for sustainable plastic products. One entrepreneur was working in the fishing industry and realized that the piles of used or damaged fishing nets could be a valuable resource due to growing demand for marine plastic. Another entrepreneur in the consumer product industry was triggered to invest in material development to fully shift their products to recycled marine plastics.

Beyond public awareness, a key driver for this group are other businesses who want to use marine plastic in their products. A startup noted 'we have only just started now, and we already have a large [customer base] who wants to buy' (NetsRecycler). Another said they were 'positively astonished about the behavior of big stock companies. . . some are greenwashing, but others really mean it. . . and if you have a CEO who pushes it, it's much easier' (MarketDeveloper2). The same company claimed that 'in the past 18 months, we have received more than 200 requests by brands' (MarketDeveloper2). Every interview reported similar levels of growing interest and positive market response to recycled marine plastics.

Beyond sales, these companies in particular mentioned the importance of investors and capital in setting up new supply chains. This is costly work requiring extensive research, material testing, traveling to collection and processing sites and developing partner relationships. Those that had access to funds reported much smoother setup procedures than those without. 'The bottleneck is finance because we are working with machinery and technology. . . so financing the whole project in the first few years is a big issue' (MarketDeveloper2). Even with sufficient customer demand, without investors or capital these companies would have been unable to develop the supply chains. High upfront costs were reportedly less of a problem for those companies focused on only one stage of the value chain, such as purely collection or recycling, than those operating on multiple stages.

The companies all rely on partnerships for sourcing, and the collected plastic comes from NGO or community organized cleanups or from the fishing or waste management industries. Startups that focus on the latter group (industry) rely on standard economic relationships, based on sales of materials or payments for disposal. Conversely, startups that partner with community-based organizations and NGOs conducted financial transactions, but also invested in activities such as infrastructure development, education and community improvements.

Despite growing interest in recycled plastic, such as yarns or pellets, the costs are still prohibitive for some potential buyers. 'Businesses want to be sustainable, or at least want to have this claim to be sustainable. But then when you talk about prices, and you explain that the fisherman has to earn something, the social enterprise people have to earn something, we have to earn something. . . it must cost at least twice as much as virgin plastic' (MarketDeveloper2). The high price may scare off interested buyers, who then may choose to pay cheaper prices for less sustainable raw materials. A few interviews noted the increasing threat of knockoffs claiming to be marine plastics and undercutting true sustainable companies.

Developing a strong value chain for recycled plastic is ultimately hampered by the technical challenges of dealing with marine plastic as a raw material. Ocean or coastal recovered plastic tends to be mixed, degraded and contaminated. Multiple companies mentioned that finding partners to process their plastic was the biggest hurdle,

since they all said 'no, don't come with ocean plastic, that will ruin our machines. . .it's dirty' (MarketDeveloper2). Cleaning, processing and exporting this material also can be energy intensive and involve shipping materials across the globe. Some companies combat this by trying to keep supply chains short, but many rely on waste collected in the developing world that is then shipped to Europe or North America – which is costly and contributes to greenhouse gas emissions.

Setting up a supply chain also requires engaging with plenty of bureaucratic procedures, such as shipping materials across borders, especially due to the 'cracking down of waste shipments' (Fishing-Nets), or applying for patents for new blends of recycled materials. This may involve 'unfair tariffs and taxes. . .that can really throw off our margins' (MarketDeveloper1). Unlike the previous BM category, the companies in the value chain category often did not receive government support, and one interviewee said they were very 'disappointed by the public sector (MarketDeveloper2). Value chain development was seen as a business opportunity more than a public service, and this could be a reason for limited institutional support.

A key concern for this group of startups is labels and certifications. These companies need a trusted and communicative brand story for their marketing, but this has led to a complicated mix of definitions. Companies may use the terms marine, ocean, ocean-bound, coastal or orphaned plastic, with conflicting definitions depending on the company. Therefore, terminology needs to be standardized. Furthermore, export and processing regulations are currently unequipped to account for the unique characteristics of recovered marine plastic material: 'this [is] such a unique operation, government agencies and permitting agencies and customs don't really know where we fit' (MarketDeveloper1). The startups interviewed are in favor of comprehensive waste trade regulations, but mention the need for standards that can enable, not impede, the development of a global marine plastic supply chain. This also applies to certification standards, such as food grade certification, which currently cannot apply to marine plastics.

The process of scaling the environmental and economic benefits of the companies involved is done by increasing the capacity of the value chain to meet increasing demand. Once key logistics and processes are developed, new supply partners can plug in to the existing infrastructures. Opening subsidiaries or offering licensing opportunities were brought up as ways to expand successful value chains to different locations. This can contribute to economies of scale and cost reductions, while also increasing environmental benefits by providing services in more areas and engaging with more communities.

4.5. Funding plastic waste recovery

The final BM category is focused on using innovative financing models to fund plastic cleanups and waste management and contains 15% of the total cases. The companies utilize offset systems, ad revenues or sales of products to gain profit, and then redirect funds to support cleanup efforts. Around half of the 14 companies are also engaged with transformation of the collected waste and developing monitoring tools. To access funds, the businesses are dependent on continued support from users or customers, and many cases deploy subscription models to try and secure steady, monthly revenue from their customers. Other revenue models are focused on plastic credits, which work similar to carbon credits or offsets: a company or brand determines the amount of plastic used in their business operations and pays to have a similar amount of waste removed from the environment. All of the companies operating this model are dependent on external partners to deliver environmental value. They rely on third-party organizations who engage in beach cleanups, set up waste banks and develop waste management infrastructure.

The entrepreneurs interviewed have similar perspectives on why their companies are necessary: in many places, waste management services are ineffective or absent and private companies are needed to fill this gap. These startups are focused on using innovative revenue models to provide these services. The entrepreneurs realized they could harness public concern about plastic into a financial opportunity. Some startups develop software solutions, focusing on the accountability systems necessary to track plastic waste and provide incentives for collection. Others spend resources on developing hardware technology and machinery that could process plastic waste locally. One company said they are 'more a . . .solution provider than an offsetting scheme, we use the offsetting basically to pay for the development of what we do' (FinancingWaste2). This was reiterated by all interviewees, that the revenue models are merely a means to supply waste management services and solutions. That being said, each company did bring up the importance of financial capital in setting up infrastructure in the beginning of their operations, be it from angel investors, venture capital or government grants.

Partnerships are also critical for these companies, as they engage with community groups on the ground to set up clean-up efforts or waste banks, as well as treatment partners who can accept or recycle the collected waste. One interview mentioned that good processing partners 'are like gold when you find one' (FinancingWaste1). The operations are constrained by the infrastructures and technological capacity of the countries they work in and the materials they manage. For example, multiple entrepreneurs described how there are 'no good landfills' (FinancingWaste2) in the regions they operate. One startup therefore delivers collected waste for incineration, while another has developed small scale recycling systems so that the communities can process their waste locally. However, the same interviewee admitted that this still leaves some unrecyclable or toxic residual waste, which they currently have no good end-of-life solution for.

Efficiency and effectiveness were frequently mentioned by the interviewees. They recognize that developing household waste collection services or improving landfills is much more effective than removing waste from the environment. However, the public and investors are attracted to the story and branding of collected ocean plastic. This creates a paradox where doing what is good for business is not necessarily what is better for the environment, and the startups must work to collect marine plastic, even when land-based management is more effective. One company tackles this by including community education and infrastructure development projects alongside their marine plastic collection efforts. Another works with local waste pickers to set up household collection services in order to reduce the amount of waste leaked into the environment. The entrepreneurs recognize that collected marine plastic 'has a charismatic, beautiful story' (FinancingWaste1), which is key to attracting finance. They try to harness the power of this story, but then mainly divert funding towards effective strategies because 'collecting one ton of plastic waste out of the ocean is just so much more work' (FinancingWaste2).

These companies are, by necessity or design, developing tracking software and processes in order to monitor the collected plastic as it moves from the environment through aggregation, processing and recycling to its end-of-life destination. Currently, most companies develop their own tools for this, leading to high complexity and fragmentation of standards and monitoring: 'Until this market is regulated through standards, we will continue to see different kinds of companies trying to come up with their own standards.' (FinancingWaste2). Adding to the complexity are the vast differences in global waste management systems and the lack of standardized metrics for waste. The startups are working to develop tools that are streamlined and data-driven, and there may be opportunities to integrate the systems and processes already developed by startups into future institutional certifications and standards.

Fig. 2. Synthesizing drivers and barriers based on interviews with entrepreneurs and experts.

4.6. Synthesizing drivers and barriers

Synthesizing the drivers and barriers mentioned by the interviewees in the different BM categories, we present an integrated framework in Fig. 2 showing the factors which are experienced by all ventures, and those related to a specific BM.

We find that the entrepreneurial drivers and barriers were experienced by all startups, regardless of the BM deployed. Entrepreneurial ambition, sustainability motivation and dedication to the cause were mentioned by many interviewees. The entrepreneurs are not in the industry ‘to get rich, then I would have joined a completely different industry... but we want to solve the problem and to take money from the brands to pay for it’ (FinancingWaste2). These entrepreneurs are individuals who saw opportunities for solving a global problem and then devoted their time and energy to commercialize solutions. For many this meant doing something completely new, as one noted ‘we never really wanted to make equipment. It was only because there was no equipment out there that fit what I needed’ (FinancingWaste1). All entrepreneurs have struggled at various times with the process of creating a new business, and for many, this was their first experience with entrepreneurship or even the private sector. For the new entrepreneurs, this meant that business administration, searching for finance and attracting and hiring staff were all new challenges. Interviewees mentioned that as their company grew, they faced a bottleneck in finding dedicated and capable people to join their teams. These entrepreneurial drivers and barriers align well with established sustainable entrepreneurship literature.

Main drivers identified include societal awareness and public outcry around marine plastic pollution, described as the ‘major shift that happened in 2016’ of (FinancingWaste1). This cultural shift led to the creation of entrepreneurial opportunities because it signaled market demand and political support for marine plastic solutions. Since this is a relatively new field, many entrepreneurs have found pioneer advantage to work in their favor: the market is not yet overcrowded and therefore it can be relatively easier to find customers and

generate brand recognition. Financial support is critical, but can come in many forms such as government grants, private investments or crowdfunding. Technical drivers were found to be BM specific and not generally applicable to all cases.

Regarding barriers, although the attention given to new marine plastic startups has generated brand recognition and sales, it has also led to the rise of knockoffs and copycats. When asked about competition, the entrepreneurs explicitly welcomed more solution providers to tackle marine plastic, however, they are worried about the introduction of less-sustainable or less-effective imitation products and services, in other words ‘diluting the message of sustainability’ (Niessen & Bocken, 2021, p. 1098). These lower quality offerings are cheaper, and cost-cutting and greenwashing affects the legitimacy of the entire industry. ‘We feel that a lot of companies want to become more sustainable, but some would like to have a sort of greenwashing for as cheap a price as they are paying now for virgin plastic’ (MarketDeveloper2). This sense of competition is not only present in the marketplace, but also in the media. Many interviewees mentioned the ‘hype’ around plastic, and since the topic has gone viral in the media, there is now competition for attention. Competitors are ‘financing social media campaigns so that they can get as many marketing clicks and be in front of everyone’s face online’ (MarketDeveloper1). Regulatory agencies can fight greenwashing by increasing standardization and metrics, which is currently lacking, and institutions are frequently cited as being too slow to properly regulate and support the emerging marine plastic management industry.

5. Discussion and conclusions

5.1. Implications for research

Our study suggests that the choice of BM influences has implications for the sustainable entrepreneurship journey and enabling conditions differ depending on the BM. The BM categories also confirm that sustainable value creation is not uniform but occurs in a wide

variety of ways, and that different types of environmental benefits are related to different BM designs (Hahn et al., 2018). Our results also suggest that there is added-value in researching clusters of entrepreneurs based on their BMs (Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2019). We were able to determine BM clusters using information available online, and could group business cases as a preparatory step before getting in contact with startups or entrepreneurs. This approach could be useful for others engaging in BM or entrepreneurship research and studying a large sample of cases. Our study also supports the conceptualization of a BM not as a static state but an ongoing process (Dembek et al., 2018). BMs initiated by entrepreneurs are often a moving target, and the BM is modified throughout the entrepreneurial journey. For example, interview respondents often mention the importance of accessing finance and capital in the beginning stages of their business development, with a focus on economic value capture, whereas later on there is a shift towards delivering higher levels of environmental benefits. Future research could investigate how value prioritization changes throughout the entrepreneurial journey.

Another angle that was not covered in the present study is the comparison of actions and obstacles concerning individual business versus those related to collective goals or challenges (Planko, Cramer, Chappin & Hekkert, 2016). These companies are focused on a collective challenge of marine plastic pollution, and some goals are clearly related specifically to this collective problem whereas others are more related to new venture development. We conceptualize the differences between different business models, however a more explicit focus on individual and collective contexts would be a useful contribution to the field. We also asked the entrepreneurs about their sustainability goals, however there are variety of other motivations, such as improved quality of life, that can drive an entrepreneur (Martin Martin and Guaita Martínez, 2020). Especially considering that environmental challenges can threaten current or future quality of life, it would be worth further study to see how personal ambitions beyond profit and environment contribute to venture development.

Furthermore, our sample was comprised of a subset of blue entrepreneurs focused only on marine plastics. Future research could expand this to account for other marine focused sustainable ventures, for example, those working on ocean renewable energy, fishing and aquaculture, and maritime transport. There is growing political support and investment in the Blue Economy, and many innovations are being led by startups and small businesses in this field. Follow up studies can build upon our work to identify the enabling environment for blue entrepreneurs in general by using a wider variety of case studies.

5.2. Recommendations for policy and practice

We found a number of influencing factors that were experienced by entrepreneurs regardless of the BM deployed, suggesting some enablers and obstacles are likely to be experienced by many companies working on marine plastic. Reducing barriers can contribute to a wider adoption of innovations introduced by startups, and policy-makers should prioritize three interventions. First, policy makers should provide targeted support for marine plastic companies, such as through accelerators or incubators offering business training for new entrepreneurs. Beyond training, which is useful for inexperienced entrepreneurs, the second priority is financing in the early stages of business development. As one entrepreneur explained, no amount of business training can help overcome the costs of setting up a startup and hiring necessary staff. Relevant sources of financing can come from government funding for feasibility studies or pilot projects, and efforts should be made to lower the administrative burden while applying for these funds. Third, government standardization can help stimulate and regulate the growing industry. Government-backed standards for monitoring and labeling will

increase transparency, but also provide a benchmark that startups and investors can use to compare solutions to one another. Globally accepted and understood terminology will reduce complexity and prevent greenwashing, which ultimately will benefit consumers and increase legitimacy in the industry.

For entrepreneurs or practitioners, our findings suggest two areas where startups should devote resources and attention. First, developing human resources strategies and finding quality staff should be prioritized. Previous research has found that the 'liability of newness' surrounding startups may be a barrier to attracting candidates (Thompson & Eijkemans, 2018). This can be tempered by developing human resources strategies that demonstrate the career potential and non-monetary benefits of working at a sustainable company, such as personal development and providing services to society. Second, collective efforts are needed for institutional shaping. Since governments are seen as a barrier due to a slow policy response and lack of appropriate standards and regulations, institutional change is necessary. Startups can work to shape the institutional landscape by engaging with relevant government actors. However, these activities require time and resources (Pacheco, Dean & Payne, 2010). Pooling resources by partnering with other companies or initiatives engaging in marine plastic management is one avenue to reduce transaction costs and increase bargaining power.

5.3. Limitations

Our research strategy includes limitations, some of which we have tried to address. First, our sample of business cases is not exhaustive and may not be completely representative of the true extent and spread of the marine plastic management industry. This is due to the reliance on company web pages for information. There may be more small businesses managing marine plastic that do not have an online presence and would be missed from our searching. Second, we interviewed only 20% of the businesses from our database, and our interviewees may not be fully representative of the 96 business cases. We purposefully selected interviewees operating different BM categories to support a diverse response group. We also included expert interviews to validate our data analysis and provide additional information on trends in the industry. To enhance the generalizability of our results, future research could test our assumptions with a wider group of entrepreneurs, for example using an online survey.

Another limitation is our focus thus far on the environmental and economic pillars of sustainability. Some companies in our sample reported to be social enterprises or explicitly mentioned social impacts, however it was not discussed nearly as much as environmental and economic. Oftentimes, social benefits are seen as a product of economic outcomes, such as job creation, or environmental benefits, such as a cleaner community due to less plastic pollution. This shortcoming is also present in some conceptualizations of the Blue Economy that focus on the oceans as a business opportunity and an environmental resource to utilize, rather than a social and cultural resource (Voyer et al., 2018). Marine plastic pollution has clear negative impacts on people and communities, but the deployment of strategies to manage marine plastic will also have an impact. Academics have already called attention to the fact that companies are not merely influenced by socio-cultural factors, but are integrated in social systems (Muñoz & Cohen, 2018). As the field of blue entrepreneurship develops, it will be fruitful to study both negative, positive, intended and unintended social impacts, for example how social sustainability can increase competitiveness (Guaita Martínez, Martín, Ribeiro Soriano & Salinas Fernández, 2021).

5.4. Concluding remarks

This research paper provided an overview of BM categories and their associated enabling conditions for a sample of blue

entrepreneurs focused on marine plastic mitigation. We found four categories of BMs, including consumer targeted solutions, government and business solutions, companies focused on value chain development, and startups that generate revenue to fund plastic waste recovery. These four BMs differ in how they create environmental benefits, as well as their economic value capture or revenue models. Interviews with 18 entrepreneurs operating these different business models demonstrated that the entrepreneurial challenges and motivations associated with starting a new business are experienced by all companies, regardless of the business model chosen. Other relevant drivers include the availability of financing early on in business development, a supportive culture and positive and constructive market response. Challenges include competition from less sustainable businesses that may negatively influence the legitimacy of the industry, as well as slow government responses. Our results suggest policymakers should prioritize offering entrepreneurial support to new ventures, including financial support, as well as harmonizing labels, terminology and standards. Future research can expand the scope of the study to cover different segments of the Blue Economy, and could also consider other stakeholder groups such as the public sector and civil society groups, who are also providing critical marine plastic mitigation services.

Finally, we must stress that entrepreneurial ventures cannot provide all of the actions needed mitigate marine plastic pollution (Kuckertz, Berger & Brändle, 2020). Municipalities are needed to invest in pollution control and regulation of virgin plastic production and conventional plastic producers, manufacturers and brands must shift towards sustainable plastic options. Consumers and citizens on a global scale must support political action, while also choosing sustainable options. NGOs and researchers are also needed to advocate

for change and provide evidence on the magnitude of the problem and potential solutions (Silva, Rosano, Stocker & Gorissen, 2017; ten Brink et al., 2018). That being said, it is evident that entrepreneurs can contribute by demonstrating the viability of new BMs, producing technologies, coordinating new supply chains and pioneering infrastructures.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded under the EU project CLAIM (Cleaning Litter by developing and Applying Innovative Methods in European seas) H2020 Grant agreement ID: 774586.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.stae.2022.100018.

Appendices

- Appendix 1 – Variables included in the analytical framework.
- Appendix 2 – Semi-structured interview guide.

Appendix 1

	Variables	Definition	
Sustainable business model components	Value proposition	Unique product or service offering	
	Economic	How monetary benefits or profits are created Who participates in delivering economic value	
	Ecological	Value creation and delivery Stakeholders involved	Cost structure and revenue model
		Value capture	How environmental benefits are created Who participates in delivering environmental value
Factors influencing sustainable entrepreneurship	Internal factors	Environmental monitoring and impact measurement	
		Entrepreneurial	Drivers and barriers associated with starting a new company and the characteristics of the entrepreneur
	External factors	Technical	Drivers and barriers associated with technology development
		Economic and market Institutional and regulatory Socio-cultural	Drivers and barriers associated with economic conditions and market support Drivers and barriers associated with political conditions and institutional support Drivers and barriers associated with societal conditions and public support

Appendix 1

Topic	Questions (s)
Business model	Can you describe the business model for company? - Value proposition - Customers - Production - Costs and revenues
Technology	What role does technology play in your business? Is there an important technology that is needed for your business to run? How was this technology developed? Is technology a key driver or barrier to your business development?
Regulatory	Do institutions (government/EU/UN agencies, regulatory bodies) play a role in your business? Was there certain legislation or regulations that contributed to your business development? Have you had institutional support or financing for your business development? Is institutional support a key driver for your businesses? Has regulation or legislation been a barrier to your business development?
Economic and market	Do other private sector actors play a role in your business (business partners, shared knowledge etc.)? Have private sector actors contributed to financing your business development? Such as banks, incubators, donors etc. Have you had conflict or competition with other private sector actors or companies (sustainable or incumbent)

(continued)

Appendix 1 (Continued)

Topic	Questions (s)
Socio-cultural	Have economic or market conditions been key drivers or barriers to your business development?
	Do you collaborate with other companies or businesses?
	Public awareness and offense about plastic has increased in the last few years, how have you felt this? Has it led to increasing demand and/or competition for your technology?
	Do you participate in societal engagement? Such as advocacy or education?
	Have NGOs or community groups contributed to your business development?
Environmental impact	Have NGOs been a barrier to your business development?
	Does your company interact with NGOs or communities to provide them with information, advice or services?
	Have social or cultural context been a key driver to your business development?
General	How does your business affect the environment? What is your environmental impact? What do you measure? What could be improved?
	Is your business dependent on the environment?
General	What is your interaction with the environment?
	What is your definition of a sustainable business?
	Do you consider your company to be a sustainable business?
	What was the motivation for creating a sustainable business?
	What are the benefits of being a sustainable business?
	What are the drawbacks?
	Where do you place your business on the organizational life cycle?
	Is there anything you'd like to add?

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